

IPAD-MD
Deliverable 4.2 (WP4)

Report on
Complementary RI
and User Communities
in Africa

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Table of Contents:

1. Introduction	1
2. Outreach to complementary RIs	2
<i>a. 'Outreach to Africa' at IPAD-MD Kick-off Meeting (Munich, 21-22 July 2015) and D6.1 IPAD-MD Expert Group Meeting on Standards & Technology (CNR-Monterotondo, Nov. 18, 2015)</i>	2
<i>b. Report on on-site visit at the University of Cape Town (UCT) Core Unit (SPF breeding & Biotechnology Laboratory), 26-31 October 2017</i>	2
<i>c. Successful material exchange between UCT and EMMA</i>	3
<i>d. Interaction with UCT Animal Facility</i>	3
<i>e. Overview of the South African RI Roadmap (SARIR)</i>	4
<i>f. Interaction with ICGEB</i>	5
3. Outreach to User Communities	5
<i>a. IPAD-MD/INFRAFRONTIER TWG's Members attendance at SAALAS Conference 2017</i>	5
<i>b. INFRAFRONTIER at the Drug Safety Africa Conference 2018</i>	5
4. Outcome	6
<i>a. Inclusion of UCT in PathBio</i>	6
<i>b. UCT's letter of intent to become an INFRAFRONTIER partner</i>	6
<i>c. Integration for UCT into INFRAFRONTIER projects - additional funding and resources.</i>	7
5. Annex	8
<i>a. Report on the UCT Core Unit visit</i>	8
<i>b. UCT Letter of Intent to INFRAFRONTIER</i>	13

1. Introduction

One of the objectives of IPAD-MD is to reach out to complementary infrastructures and user communities in Africa in order to increase the reach of INFRAFRONTIER and EMMA resources and services.

WP4 (in collaboration with WP2) was tasked with the identification of complementary research infrastructures and user communities in Africa primarily from interactions with the African stakeholders associated with the IPAD-MD meetings and activities. This would give a more detailed picture about the human/mouse genetics community in Africa, potential complementary research infrastructures and user communities including information on the specific requirements of potential African users for mouse resources and data.

According to PAERIPs initial report on African and European infrastructures¹, the African Consolidated Plan of Action identified four programme areas which may benefit from access to (European) RI for their implementation:

- Biodiversity, Biotechnology and Indigenous Knowledge
- Energy, Water and Desertification
- Material Sciences, Manufacturing, Laser and Post-Harvest Technologies
- Information and Communication Technologies and Space Science and Technologies

Biotechnology is one of the main programmes for future African RIs and INFRAFRONTIER via the IPAD-MD stakeholder and expert group meetings, identified the Animal Research Facility at University of Cape Town and North West University's Preclinical Drug Development Program (PCDDP) as two promising first contact points to reach out to African RIs and user communities.

This report details the progress made by INFRAFRONTIER using IPAD-MD funded activities to establish consequential and relevant ties to complementary African researchers.

¹ Preliminary findings on African and European Research Infrastructure that support potential partnerships between the two continents, A P Botha, and G von Gruenewaldt, January 2012, Version 2.0

2. Outreach to complementary RIs

a. 'Outreach to Africa' at IPAD-MD Kick-off Meeting (Munich, 21-22 July 2015) and D6.1 IPAD-MD Expert Group Meeting on Standards & Technology (CNR-Monterotondo, Nov. 18, 2015)

Dr. Frank Brombacher (University of Cape Town & International Centre for Genetic Engineering and Biotechnology) was invited to the IPAD-MD Kick-off Meeting in Munich (July 2015) and presented the mission, strategic goals, composition and funding instruments of the International Centre for Genetic Engineering and Biotechnology (ICGEB), as well as the current research infrastructures available in Africa, its users and their needs. Scientifically, ICGEB and African users focus on immunology and infection diseases (e.g. Tuberculosis) and drug and vaccination target discovery. In terms of opportunities to cooperate with INFRAFRONTIER, emphasis was set to the archiving and distribution of mouse models by means of training in cryopreservation technologies. This led to K. Coulson's (Responsible Reproduction Biotechnologist, University of Cape Town) participation in the CNR-INFRAFRONTIER-EMMA Monterotondo Cryopreservation Course and Workshop on Assisted Reproductive Technologies (Nov. 7-10, 2016) that was funded by IPAD-MD.

The WP6 S&T Expert Group Meeting (CNR-Monterotondo, November 2015) included a session dedicated to 'Outreach to Africa'. Dr. Susan Marschall (HMGU-IEG) reviewed the Kick-off Meeting's outcomes and current knowledge of African infrastructures and user communities/needs. The ensuing WP6 experts' discussion identified main priorities for the envisaged interactions, including the need for INFRAFRONTIER/EMMA assisted training of the prospective University of Cape Town partner's group in advanced cryopreservation and dissemination techniques as well as planning/testing of specific workflows/procedures. This was aimed at establishing an Archiving & Distribution node of disease model strains in Africa, with attainment of the required international standards and service levels. An on-site visit and report by expert INFRAFRONTIER/EMMA delegates, according to the approved Consortium's Guidelines was also planned and it took place in October 2017 (see following point).

b. Report on on-site visit at the University of Cape Town (UCT) Core Unit (SPF breeding & Biotechnology Laboratory), 26-31 October 2017

IPAD-MD funded the on-site visit of UCT's Core Unit by Dr. Marcello Raspa (CNR) to assess opportunities and risks, estimate unit's current and future capacities, potential expansion, etc. (see details in the attached Report – Annex 5a). The UCT GEM Core unit and biotechnology lab was found to be quite well organised but needing better implementation to make use of its full potential. Animal colonies were found well maintained with an excellent quality standard thanks to efficient supervision and the professionalism of the personnel involved in applying the procedures and protocols. The biotechnology lab required to be organised in more efficient and practical way to fully meet the needs of national and pan-African scientific communities within academic and private institutions. The UCT Core Unit was considered not yet fully ready to be part of INFRAFRONTIER network whilst it could potentially implement procedural/workflow changes and upgrades to expand its capacities and rapidly achieve a fully operative status at the national and international levels. It was therefore suggested to rapidly and consistently implement the recommended changes and upgrades of procedures, equipment and protocols, especially in the biotechnology unit, and to continue the specialized education and training programs of UCT staff members and coordinators, as initially occurred with K. Coulson's participation in the CNR- INFRAFRONTIER-EMMA Monterotondo Cryopreservation Course and Workshop 2016. In this perspective, it was also proposed to have the UCT staff involved in the European initiatives led by the INFRAFRONTIER/IPAD-MD Consortia. An updated UCT facility review was also recommended once the implementation process would be completed and the unit would be ready to be part of the INFRAFRONTIER RI, as its South Africa node. In this context it was also suggested to test the exchange of mutant mouse lines, with reference INFRAFRONTIER partners, through shipment/importation/testing of frozen/refrigerated and live products (see below and details in the attached Report – Annex 5a).

c. Successful material exchange between UCT and EMMA

Frozen mouse sperms and embryos were sent to the Centre of Research Animal, UCT by INFRAFRONTIER-EMMA Cryopreservation Unit at Helmholtz Centre Munich to test their rederivation and cryopreservation protocols on October 2016 which was successful. As stated above, this was mentioned in 'Conclusions and Recommendations' in the UCT Core Unit visit report (Annex 5a) with next step being the transfer and rederivation of germplasm from UCT at an INFRAFRONTIER partner node. This material exchange was carried out to integrate UCT in the EMMA network as an EMMA node for Africa.

d. Interaction with UCT Animal Facility

UCT Research Animal Facility provides training across Africa in terms of basic animal handling, housing and care. According to Dr. Bert Mohr, Director of UCT Research Animal Facility, there are very few dedicated mouse facilities in Africa that can engage INFRAFRONTIER / EMMA services like model generation, archiving and strain distribution. In addition, UCT has a recently upgraded cryopreservation service in accordance to EMMA standards. This facility is open to external customers but very few facilities and institutes are in a position to use it. Some of those who can have already been engaged in the context of IPAD-MD like PCDDP at NWU.

e. Overview of the South African RI Roadmap (SARIR)

A South African Research Infrastructure Roadmap (SARIR) has been developed to facilitate a national and global research infrastructure programme in South Africa with the intention to ‘provide a strategic, rational, long term framework for planning, implementing, monitoring and evaluating the provision of research infrastructures (RIs) necessary for a competitive and sustainable national system of innovation’². In theory, this roadmap also lays the foundation for collaborating with international RIs like INFRAFRONTIER. The initial list of RIs belonged to six scientific domains: (i) humans and society, (ii) health, biological and food security, (iii) Earth and environment, (iv) materials and manufacturing, (v) energy and (vi) physical sciences and engineering. However, after a comprehensive and robust assessment process, the following seven RIs were approved for establishment in the 2016/17 financial year:

- An expanded terrestrial and freshwater environmental observation network;
- A nuclear medicine research facility;
- A South African network of health and demographic surveillance sites;
- A national centre for digital language resources;
- A Natural science collections facility;
- Shallow marine and coastal research infrastructure;
- Distributed platform for “omics” research.

² South African Research Infrastructure Roadmap, Department of Science and Technology, October 2016

SARIR places special emphasis on establishing collaborations with international communities and research networks in order to make South Africa a viable destination for investment in science and technology. The “omics” RI platform includes genomics, proteomics, metabolomics and bioinformatics and are the most closely related to INFRAFRONTIER.

f. Interaction with ICGEB

IPAD-MD promoted and supported successful networking activities with ICGEB headquarters and African components of ICGEB. This contributed to the subsequent preparation and submission of a new ICGEB grant application to support a seminar next year on gene modification and cryopreservation at UCT, with the involvement of partners IPAD-MD and other important African institutions, including Egypt, Tunisia, Kenya, Nigeria, Algeria, etc. The application will be evaluated according to the concurrent pandemic eruption and evolution. This event can be the first step of the creation of a pan-African network.

3. Outreach to User Communities

a. IPAD-MD/INFRAFRONTIER TWG’s Members attendance at SAALAS Conference 2017

IPAD-MD funded Dr. Jesus Ruberte Paris (UAB) and Dr. Marcello Raspa (CNR) participation in the South African Association for Laboratory Animal Science (SAALAS) International Conference 2017 (Cape Town, Nov. 1-3) where they presented information about the INPATH/PathBio International Consortium in Integrative Mouse Pathobiology and INFRAFRONTIER/EMMA’s contribution to 3Rs, respectively, including latest advancements in cryopreservation/dissemination techniques etc., directed towards the significant reduction in the number of animals utilized in laboratory experimentation. This led, in particular, to the associated partnership of University of Cape Town’s Research Animal Facility in the PathBio Knowledge Alliance project’s proposal, which has been successfully funded by the European Union’s Erasmus+ Programme (please refer to 4a below). In addition, the TWG members also attended and contributed to the post-conference workshop on ‘Establishing the pan-African LAS network’.

b. INFRAFRONTIER at the Drug Safety Africa Conference 2018

Dr. Asrar Ali Khan represented INFRAFRONTIER as an invited speaker at the first Drug Safety Africa Conference 2018 (20 – 22 November 2018, Potchefstroom) at the North-West University. The conference was hosted by the Preclinical Drug Development Program (PCDDP) and presented high quality lectures on safety pharmacology, toxicology, clinical drug safety and precision medicine from international academic and industry experts. EMMA’s impressive catalogue of mouse models for human diseases (applicable in drug safety studies) were showcased in Dr. Ali Khan’s talk along with an introduction to INFRAFRONTIER as a European Research Infrastructure for mouse models. The IPAD-MD project was also presented with regard to its activities involving ‘reaching out to complementary infrastructures and user communities in Africa’. Other avenues under INFRAFRONTIER’s ‘Outreach to Africa’ were also highlighted like transnational access calls (INFRAFRONTIER 2020), stakeholder meetings, online knowledgebase, trainings and workshops. The conference report was accepted in the Journal of Pharmacological and Toxicological Methods in April 2019 and published in August 2019³.

4. Outcome

a. Inclusion of UCT in PathBio

PathBio (<http://pathbio.org>) is an ERASMUS+ Knowledge Alliance consortium constituted at the European level to develop a strong educational program for Mouse Precision Pathobiology. Phenogenomics centres from Asia, South America, Australia and Africa provide PathBio with an outstanding skillset and in-depth knowledge on using mouse models to validate human diseases. As mentioned above, the IPAD-MD funded activities set up the stage for University of Cape Town’s Research Animal Facility to become one of the contributing African phenogenomics centres.

b. UCT’s letter of intent to become an INFRAFRONTIER partner

Please refer to Annex 5b.

³ **Drug safety Africa: An overview of safety pharmacology & toxicology in South Africa**
<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1056871919300395>

c. Integration for UCT into INFRAFRONTIER projects - additional funding and resources.

From the various IPAD-MD activities directed towards outreach to Africa, it has become evident that there is substantial interest and research work in mouse models in the African continent, especially South Africa. On the basis of these activities, UCT would be an important EMMA node and an integral INFRAFRONTIER member. In order to provide funds for this integration, WP4 of the newly submitted INFRADEV-03-2018-2019 project proposal will focus on the enlargement of INFRAFRONTIER membership in Africa and will start with an updated reassessment of UCT's Centre for Animal Research with another site visit and material transfer test (as mentioned in Annex 5a).

5. Annex

a. Report on the UCT Core Unit visit

Report on site visit by M. Raspa of the UCT (University of Cape Town) Core Unit (SPF Breeding & Biotechnology laboratory) - Cape Town, 26-31 October 2017

Date: 31st October 2017

Object

Evaluate opportunities and risks, explore possibilities to expand the Core Unit and offer internal and external services, at both national and international/pan-African level (independently and as a South African member of INFRAFRONTIER/IPAD-MD Consortia). Estimate and assess the unit's capacities (current and future); figure out potential activities/services to be established/expanded according to the present assessment.

Preamble

The SPF Core Unit has been functioning in the Werner and Beit Building at the University of Cape Town (UCT) since 2005. The SPF unit encompasses the basement level of the building on the UCT Faculty of Health Sciences Campus, Cape Town (South Africa). The Core Unit is organised in two SPF areas (SPF1 and SPF2) and (separate) quarantine where sanitary procedures have been working well since many years (different staff and dedicated procedures). The nine staff members of the SPF unit are mostly split into the two main sections (SPF 1 and SPF 2). The SPF 1 staff consist of the SPF Manager, Mr Jabu Magagula, two Technical Assistants (TA, supervisory role), two Animal Attendants (AA) and one Departmental Assistant (DA supportive role). These staff are responsible for maintaining mice in individually ventilated cages (IVCs) in three animal rooms, each with its own HEPA filtered cage changing station (CCS), as well as in the SPF quarantine. The SPF 2 staff consist of one Reproduction Biotechnologist, one TA and one AA. These staff maintain mice in IVCs in two animal rooms, each with their own CCS, as well as in six isolators. The Reproduction Biotechnologist, Mrs Kerith Coulson, is in charge of the cryopreservation and embryo transfer program with the assistance of the other two staff members. At present the laboratory has one laminar flow cabinet, one large CO₂ incubator, a stereo microscope, an inverted microscope and a combination laboratory fridge and -20°C freezer. The transfer room inside the barrier section houses two IVC racks attached to a Techniplast blower, a CCS, laminar flow cabinet and a stereo microscope, with the addition of an incubator to be delivered in early 2018. Each SPF unit has its own disinfection chamber and autoclave for introducing items into the barrier. The SPF quality standards and procedures are organised and generally effective with maintaining the laboratory animal's health status free from pathogens, at the same sanitary status attained in most European *in-vivo* experimental Core Facilities. Indeed, worth noting are the established SPF procedures (e.g. HD and ET as a method to eradicate pathogens of strains to be bred into both SPF1 and SPF2) and restrictions of these areas to investigators, without affecting/preventing full access to the services provided by the SPF unit. In 2011 the SPF unit expanded to include the Reproduction Biotechnology Laboratory which changed management in 2013. The current manager (Mrs Kerith Coulson) attended the Jackson Laboratory workshop on Embryo Transfer and Workshop on the Cryopreservation of Mouse Germplasm in May

2014. In 2016, Kerith joined the CNR-JAX-INFRAFRONTIER-EMMA Monterotondo Cryopreservation Course and Workshop on ARTs and has been corresponding with our team since then, to improve her unit's procedures and results. Approximately 100 GEM strains are successfully bred at UCT Core Unit and maintained alongside several wild-type lines, while routine import and export of laboratory animals and their products/germplasm is well established and performed. Mice of the two main background strains (BALB/cJ and C57BL/6J) were restocked in August 2012 from the Jackson Laboratory. Health standards are excellent, personnel are qualified and motivated and quality controls are regularly performed. Under this scenario, availability of more qualified services and more opportunities are encouraged, taking advantage of close and continuous collaboration with European scientific institutions and organisations (CNR-Monterotondo and other INFRAFRONTIER/IPAD-MD Consortia's members, ICGEB, etc.) to rapidly attain the required standards and therefore present the scopes and pursue the goals of INFRAFRONTIER in South Africa and the whole African continent. At this stage, more flexibility and pragmatism are considered necessary – this will lead to increased freezing and restoring of GEM lines as an UCT user service and to achieve the banking of more lines (with safety, ethical and economic value). In conclusion, the main procedures of the UCT Biotechnology Lab are well established and under development but they are still underutilised and underestimated, although with great potential (it may be a reference Lab and Core Unit for the entire Country and the whole Continent) and therefore, need to be more extensively implemented and completed.

Aim

- ✓ Offer specialised services to UCT, other South-African/continental Institutions, Investigators;
- ✓ Become an INFRAFRONTIER outstation;
- ✓ Implement specialised training & education programmes, courses and workshop/congresses (Lab animal science and GEMs);
- ✓ National and International collaborations;
- ✓ Import/export GEMs;
- ✓ Searching/generating GEMs (in collaboration);
- ✓ Other

Plan 2017-18

Biotechnology laboratory space: to be re-organised for safety and ergonomic reasons (i.e. separate LN2 tanks from working areas, free spaces and labs benches to allow the simultaneous work of two or more operators, etc.);

Procedures: sterility in the cryo-lab is not necessary (there are several papers on the field which prove the rarity of pathogen transmission through germplasm collection and storage – cryopreservation is extremely effective as pathogen eradication method with limited or no risks) whilst it is strictly recommended in the SPF unit in order to maintain the highest sanitary standards; Current procedures are generally quite complicated and fragmented: more flexibility and more forward/linear processes are needed to enhance effectiveness and capacity. All cryo-procedures should be done in the cryo-lab directly by two operators. The work for preparing media and stock solutions may be centralised in the current ICGEB lab.

Personnel: Kerith Coulson has qualified expertise on managing the lab but she has reached the point where a technician is needed to assist her (e.g. Desmond now and another qualified technical assistant for the immediate future). This person may work in parallel with her and help with the main procedures (freezing/thawing and ET) for dirty/clean preparations and set up. For example, ET is quite ineffective since embryos are exposed to lab room air for approximately an hour or more (time taken to enter SPF and prepare the surgical area and materials): this heavily affects their viability. More flexibility is required to better organize procedures during a standard working week with procedures, e.g.: ET beginning and Cryo: sperm freezing, IVF and embryo-freezing at the end of the same week.

Archiving (GEM stocks): cryo-tank/Dewar and QCs.: insufficient – to be expanded/upgraded.

Equipment: storage space is limited and no back-up system is available (large cryo-tank); the -20°C freezer temperature fluctuates periodically (needs to be replaced) and a -80°C freezer is recommended; a small incubator is necessary in SPF where ETs are performed as well as a small fridge for the storage of media/drugs. More equipment and instruments are suggested to complete the unit, such as Daisy goblets, tri-gasses MINC benchtop incubator, gas anaesthesia system, more dewars.

Protocols: to be implemented, especially with regard to IVF, media preparation and stock solutions.

Activities' Database and QCs: to be established and developed.

Site visit, audit and training/setting up procedures and protocols: UCT & CNR/INFRAFRONTIER (plan for 2018).

To be defined and optimised (Biotechnology Lab – Cryo and GEMs Core Unit):

- ✓ Protocols and methods
- ✓ Procedures
- ✓ Sperm freezing and thawing
- ✓ Embryo freezing and thawing
- ✓ IVF
- ✓ QCs
- ✓ Database system
- ✓ ET/HD
- ✓ Animal colonies
- ✓ Media preparation and stocks
- ✓ SPF Units (to be unified with the same health status)

Experiments and controls at UCT – site visit

Medium Preparation: Sperm cryopreservation medium (CPM) was prepared in the Reproduction Biotechnology Laboratory (REP Lab). The current standard operating procedure (SOP) is to add the cryoprotectant, MTG, into the stock medium batch. Medium is made in 50-ml volumes to accommodate equipment limitations as well as storage space for the frozen stocks (in LN2). It was suggested that all media be made in the Tissue culture laboratory so

that larger batches can be made which will help reduce variability between batches. A trial will need to be done regarding storage of the medium at -20°C (as storage space in LN2 is limited). It was also suggested to store CPA without the addition of MTG cryoprotectant and to only add diluted MTG on the morning of sperm freezing. This change in protocol was tested during the visit, and will be incorporated in future medium preparation. Two batches of media were made, one with MTG and one without MTG. Both were frozen in LN2.

Sperm Cryopreservation: Sperm cryopreservation was demonstrated in the REP Lab using medium that was made and frozen in LN2 on the same day. Both medium types described above were tested. The current system of sperm cryopreservation occurs in two distinct areas. This leads to the process being very fragmented and uncontrolled. The mouse is killed and dissected on one area and the cauda epididymides are processed and the sperm frozen in another. While there are no suggested improvements for either of the steps, it would be helpful, quicker and better controlled if all processes occurred in one room, e.g. the REP Lab, with a clean and dirty area segregated on one benchtop rather than in separate rooms. Straw storage may need to be reconsidered to enable quicker retrieval from the Dewar, e.g. straws stored in canes instead of singularly. In addition to this more storage is required as well as a backup storage area.

Sperm Thaw: Sperm thawing according to the Jackson Laboratory protocol was still being followed. It was suggested to follow the EMMA rescue thaw protocol which extends the straw time in a warm water bath to increase sperm motility at the time of IVF.

In Vitro Fertilization (IVF): Prior to the site visit SOPs were reviewed and some deviations in the suggested protocols discovered. During the visit it was suggested to return to the original protocol's volumes for IVF dishes. IVF from the sperm cryopreserved the day before was performed. This procedure is also fragmented and performed in two different areas. To reduce the time from sacrifice to oocyte retrieval, this process should also be performed in one room.

A number of stepwise changes in the media used for IVF are suggested. The REP Lab currently uses Cook Research Vitro Fertilization (RVF) medium which needs to be supplemented with Ca^{2+} . It is advised that GSH be added to the oocyte pre-incubation medium to increase fertilization and that MBCD be added to the capacitation dishes for sperm. In future, sperm capacitation medium should change to HTF+MBCD to eliminate the effect of BSA in the medium.

Embryo Cryopreservation: Embryos resulting from IVF were cryopreserved at the 2-cells stage. Embryo cryopreservation medium was made with added penicillin and streptomycin. This is not necessary if all medium that comes into contact with embryos is filtered before use. Embryos loaded into the cryopreservation straw are delivered into the straw between two bubbles. It is advisable to eliminate this step as the air bubbles may alter the success of the cryopreservation or thawing procedure. The stepwise controlled rate cryopreservation protocol is acceptable and straw seeding results in correct ice formation within the straw.

Embryo Thawing: The cryopreserved embryos were thawed after being housed in LN2 for a short while. Thawing success was slightly lower than expected despite the procedure being carried out correctly. It was suggested that embryo selection prior to cryopreservation be

more stringent and that embryos be cryopreserved at a later development stage, e.g. 8-cell, to increase thawing results.

Embryo Transfer: Embryos (2-cells) created from IVF were transferred into a suitable pseudo-pregnant recipient. Embryo transfer is performed inside the SPF 2 unit. There is currently no incubator in this unit (although one has been ordered) which means embryos are housed in suboptimal medium and conditions for extended periods. As well as this concern, Kerith is the only technician who works with embryos which means there is a significant delay between moving the embryos into the SPF unit and then performing the transfer. The embryos are kept in a straw in HEPES buffered medium at room temperature while Kerith showers into the facility and prepares the surgical area. The embryo transfer technique is good and, considering the conditions the embryos are exposed to, it is understandable that past results have been unpredictable and impressive that live births have been achieved. The procedure itself is a little slow, as injectable anaesthesia is used. The anaesthetic protocol may need to be revised in future to incorporate different anaesthetic and analgesic agents.

A simulation trial is required to determine the effect of the extended time of embryos in suboptimal medium and temperature conditions on blastocyst development. Unfortunately, there was not enough time to perform this test during this short site visit.

The current embryo transfer recipient is a CB6F1 mouse which is bred in a separate room as that where embryo transfers are performed. It may be advisable to consider using a CD1 mouse as a recipient and to move all recipient breeders and stocks into one room, i.e. B39.

Conclusions & Recommendations

The UCT GEM Core unit and biotechnology lab is currently quite well organised but needs better implementation to make use of its full potential. Animal colonies are well maintained with an excellent quality standard thanks to efficient supervision and the professionalism of the personnel involved in applying the procedures and protocols. The biotechnology lab should be organised in more efficient and practical way to fulfil the needs and necessities of national and pan-African scientific communities within academic and private institutions.

Briefly, the UCT Core Unit is not yet fully ready to be part of INFRAFRONTIER network whilst it can potentially implement procedural/workflow changes and upgrades to expand its capacities and rapidly achieve a fully operative status at the national and international level. We believe it can achieve this ambitious goal by 2018.

We suggest therefore to rapidly and consistently implement the recommended changes and upgrades of procedures, equipment and protocols, especially in the biotechnology unit, and of course to go on with specialised education and training programs for UCT staff and coordinators. In this perspective it will be advisable to have the UCT staff involved in the European initiatives led by the INFRAFRONTIER/IPAD-MD Consortia.

An updated UCT facility review is recommended once the above implementation process is completed and the unit is ready to be part of the INFRAFRONTIER Consortium, as its South Africa node. In this context it will be helpful to test the process of exchanging GEM lines with reference INFRAFRONTIER partners, through shipment/importation/testing of frozen/refrigerated and live products.

b. UCT Letter of Intent to INFRAFRONTIER

Director & Veterinarian: Research Animal Facility
Faculty of Health Sciences, University of Cape Town

Dr Bert Mohr

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25 November 2016

Dr. Michael Raess
General Management
INFRAFRONTIER GmbH

Dr. Marcello Raspa
EMMA-INFRAFRONTIER-IMPC
Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche, Rome

Dear Drs Raess & Raspa

Letter of Intent to Collaborate: INFRAFRONTIER - EMMA - University of Cape Town

The University of Cape Town's (UCT) Murine Reproduction Biotechnology Laboratory, located in the UCT Centre for Animal Research in the Faculty of Health Sciences, hereby express our intent to collaborate with the INFRAFRONTIER - EMMA consortium, in recognition of the University of Cape Town as the formal African and Southern African Node and Centre of Reference for distribution, cryopreservation, archiving, re-derivation and production of mouse germplasm resources and mouse disease models.

The University of Cape Town is ranked as the top university in Africa by international rankings, with the Faculty of Health Sciences being the top Health Sciences Faculty in Africa, and among the top 50 worldwide.

The UCT Centre for Animal Research in the Faculty of Health Sciences has maintained a rodent SPF unit for 16 years with testing for FELASA-listed pathogens (new SPF unit negative for all pathogens for past 5 years). We have performed rodent embryo transfer since 2004, with the dedicated SPF Reproduction Biotechnology Laboratory established in 2010, dedicated to the cryopreservation, archiving, re-derivation and production of SPF mouse lineages for biomedical models. The SPF unit imports and exports mouse strains internationally (America, Europe, Asia, Japan) several times per year, and distributes SPF rodents across South Africa, with over 15 African institutions being supplied. The UCT Centre for Animal Research maintains over 150 strains of GA mice, with a focus on infectious and non-communicable diseases prevalent in the African continent.

I include a report from our Reproduction Biotechnologist who recently attended the INFRAFRONTIER – EMMA Workshop on Assisted Reproductive Technologies at CNR, Monterotondo, Rome. Attendance at the workshop was aimed at streamlining efficiencies in assisted reproduction techniques in our laboratories. Technical proficiency was shown to be good and specific areas for refinement were identified to implement.

We look forward to your positive feedback and a longstanding relationship.

Yours sincerely,

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Bert Mohr'.

Dr Bert Mohr

“Our Mission is to be an outstanding teaching and research university, educating for life and addressing the challenges facing our society.”